

Infrared Thermographic modelling of defects in hybrid nature composite materials for new rail carbodies

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ABSTRACT

New trends in manufacturing of rail carbody shells show a demand for usage of composite structural components of monolithic or hybrid nature. Such composite carbodies will require non-destructive testing techniques to detect damage or defects during the train's maintenance phase. The current paper presents the application of optical pulsed and lockin thermography techniques, in reflection mode, as potential inspection techniques to be used on new composite rail carbodies. This task will be carried out using infrared thermography modelling with the aid of ThermoCalc 3D software. Delaminations and disbonds have been introduced into a thick composite sandwich component consisting of CFRP skins (5mm) and a PET foam core (30mm) using thermal properties based on literature. Simulations results presented in the paper, show the different heating power and time settings that were used and the number of detected defects. Both optical lockin and pulsed thermography simulations show potential in detecting defects up to 5mm in depth in the specimen. However, the component's PET foam core has proven to be an obstacle to thermal propagation thus making both techniques unable to detect deeper defects at the back wall of the sandwich.

Keywords: Non-destructive testing; Infrared Thermography modelling, ThermoCalc 3D modelling, composite rail carbodies; inspection methods for rail carbodies, CFRP-PET sandwich thermography inspection

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have found applications in transport systems especially in the aerospace and automotive industry. The weight reduction and mechanical properties that these materials offer, have also made them appealing for more recent applications in the rail industry, as means of reducing energy consumption in the rail transport sector, where there is demand for new rail carbodies made of carbon fibre or glass fibre components of monolithic or hybrid nature. Such research has been conducted by PIVOT2, GEARBODIES, CARBODIN EU funded projects [1][2][3] as well as research papers on existing prototypes [4][5]. Consequently, the advent of new composite rail carbodies will require non-destructive testing (NDT) techniques during their maintenance or even manufacturing phase, in order to identify the presence of defects or damage on structural sections, that may alter mechanical behaviour or even lead to catastrophic failure. Infrared thermography (IRT) is a well known and documented NDT technique that has widely been used to inspect composite materials [6][7], including large structures wind turbines and aircrafts [8]. IRT, has the ability to detect surface and subsurface defects in various materials and can be used under two distinctive forms a) passive and b) active [9]. Passive thermography does not require additional excitation of the inspected material due to the material usually being at different temperature than the ambient [9]. In the case of active thermography, which is also the subject of this paper, an external excitation source is required to create a temperature difference, enough to cause a thermal contrast between defective and non-defective areas of an inspected area [10].

The aim of this work is to present the potential application of optical pulsed and lockin thermography techniques for detecting damage/defects in new composite rail carbodies. Specifically, software based finite difference thermal modelling will be applied to model a sandwich component consisting of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) skins and Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) foam core that can be used as a structural section on the side walls of such prototype rail carbodies. The ability of the aforementioned thermography inspection techniques is explored based on

estimations of the two components mechanical and thermal properties from literature. The results of the inspection simulations are presented and discussed in this article. The work of the thermal simulations that were presented in the paper are actually part of a larger research work that included simulations in similar thick composite CFRP monolithic components as well. Despite this fact only the sandwich component IRT simulations are presented in the paper.

1.1 Modelling and simulations

Digital simulation tools belong to the general spectrum of Computer Aided Engineering (CAE). Typical benefits of using CAE tools are that a) they offer the capability of modelling objects that can be complex, b) they allow visualization in a risk-free environment, as well as c) being able to solve mathematical 2D and 3D problems [11]. From a mathematical perspective, thermal NDT is described by a differential equation in multilayer structures that contain defects with different thermal properties [12]. Thermography modelling may also significantly reduce research costs by first modelling potential test procedures on simulation software and then applying them in real life experimentation [13]. In the case of thermography, software simulations can enable experimentation with heating protocols and testing different heating duration times on a theoretical level, thus reducing time for lab environment experimentations. Simulation heating protocols and settings can also be used to help with the actual experimentation in a lab environment. In simple terms, thermal modelling and simulations can be used to assist experimentation in the lab as well as a proof of concept, whether certain techniques will have the ability to inspect certain materials or components. Although, simulations can save time, depending on their level of modelling detail, they can take hours compared to real life inspections that might take only a fraction of that time.

Various simulation software exist that can carry out thermal modelling. Some of these are Comsol, Ansys and ThermoCalc 3D. The latter is the software that has been used in the current research. It is a software that has been created by Tomsk University. It is designed for modelling thermal non-destructive testing and is capable of solving three-dimensional heat conduction problems of heating a 36-layer solid body containing up to 40 subsurface defects [14]. In ThermoCalc 3D, in order to model a sample, the user has to define the properties of the component to be examined. Such properties can be: overall dimensions of the modelled specimen; dimensions of the different material layers especially for composite materials; dimensions of the defects; thermal properties of the different material layers and the defects; orientation of the layers. Typically, materials defects like delaminations can be modelled as parallelepiped gaps in the material layer that inhibit the thermal properties of air or Teflon depending on the type of defects that need to be modelled.

2. MODELLING OF COMPONENTS

A sandwich composite sample was modelled in ThermoCalc 3D to replicate components that may find application in composite railway carbodies. The composition of the component was based on CFRP skins with the same material properties on both front and back sides and a PET foam core. Rows of subsurface defects, at different depths, were introduced into the design of the component starting from small dimensions of 3mm up to 31 mm in order to test the abilities of the IRT techniques in detecting defects. The defects were modelled based on delaminations in the CFRP skins themselves, including disbonds between the CFRP skins and the foam core. Such defects or damage can be caused on the sides of a rail carbody due to impact from flying ballast or compression and tension loads from vehicle acceleration or braking. Consequently, three rows of defects were modelled as delaminations on the front skin of the component (defects 1-9) while row #4 (defects 10-12) and row #5 (defects 13-15) are modelled as disbonds (see Figure 2). The component's material properties are presented in Table 1. Material thermal properties used in the simulation are presented in Table 2. A computational grid of 60 (X axis) x 60 (Y axis) x 297 (Z axis) steps were used to model the sandwich sample. Computational accuracy on the Z axis is of most importance because it is the axis where the heat flux Q will propagate through. Hence, depending on the thickness of the defects and the materials layers, additional computational steps are required to cover adequately the component. Figure 1 shows the dimensions of the defects. All defects were modelled as air gaps of 1mm thickness. The mechanical and thermal properties of the sandwich sample relied on various literature source as indicated on Table 2. Critical to the simulation of the IRT techniques is that potential inspection of a rail carbody can only be carried out with one sided access. This is a constrain that the rail operator company or carbody manufacturer might impose including the time duration of the inspection process. The 40mm thickness of the sandwich meant that the simulations would be challenging. Moreover, the 30mm thickness of the PET foam core would make the task even more challenging for thermography. The PET foam core apart from creating structural stiffness for the component, it is also a thermal insulating material. Thus, being able to detect defects on both front and back skins only in

thermography reflection mode will be extremely challenging both in the simulation as well as potential real-life measurements.

Table 1. Sandwich CFRP-PET component parameters

Sandwich CFRP-PET component	
Parameter	Value
Composition	CFRP skins, PET foam core
Model dimensions	30 x 30 x 40 mm
CF layer directions	Unidirectional 0/90, +/-45
Overall thickness	40 mm
CF skin thickness	5 mm (front & back)

Table 2. Material thermal properties used in IRT simulations

Material	Density ρ kg/m ³	Heat capacity C_p J/ kg·K	Thermal conductivity λ W/ (m·K)
Air (in thin gaps) ¹	1.2	1005	0.070
CFRP ²	1600	1200	0.8 (\perp) 7 (\parallel)
PET foam	250 ³	524 ⁴	0.047 ⁵

Figure 1. Front face of CF-PET-CF sandwich component with defects and dimensions

Figure 2. Top view of the CF-PET-CF sandwich and depth of defects

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- 1 Thermal properties for air taken from [11]
 - 2 Thermal properties for CFRP taken from [15]
 - 3 Density for PET foam was based on available PET products in the market used for rail applications
 - 4 Calculated value based on PET foam density
 - 5 Thermal conductivity values taken from [16] [17] for the specific PET densities

Two heating functions were used in the ThermoCalc 3D software. *Single square pulse heating* function corresponds to pulsed or square pulse thermography where Q_m is the pulse amplitude and t_h is the heating time, or pulse duration. The other heating function that was used is *thermal waves*. This option allows heating the sample with multiple cosine pulses simulating periodical harmonic heating which is closer to optical lock-in thermography technique. In *thermal waves* heating, the total heating time can be adjusted as well as the wave period of the heating (Q_m). The heat source was defined to be at the centre of the sample.

3. THERMAL SIMULATIONS RESULTS

The following section presents and analyses the thermal simulation experimentations that were carried on the model of the CFRP-PET sandwich component. As mentioned two different IRT techniques were used with their own different characteristics and requirements.

3.1 Optical lockin thermography simulations for the sandwich CFRP-PET component

Table 3 presents the results and settings that were used in a series of simulations that were performed on the sandwich component to check the ability of optical lockin thermography to detect the defects that have been modelled. Results from the first simulations with low power density were very satisfactory. Three detection methods were used 1) the visual thermal image that the software offers, 2) space profile plot, which is the temperature rise across a specified line-style region of interest on the grid of the specimen and 3) Delta T profiles of user defined X, Y coordinates where the defects exist versus sound areas of the component.

Defects up to 3.75mm were visually detectable through the thermal image, while row #4 defects could be detected through their temperature signal using space profile and Delta T rise. Only row #5, between the bottom CF skin and the core, remained undetected although it created a very small temperature signal below 0.001 °C. The best results in terms of temperature rise were given by simulation SL 12 with a total heating time of 120s. The reason why different experimentations were carried out was in order to improve the temperature rise of the defect spots and try to detect defects at the back wall of the component (row #5). Although, simulation SL16 gave better results in terms of ΔT in the simulations, the component reached a temperature of 145 °C compared to SL12 that reached 75 °C. The difference between the 120s heating time and 90s at 11111 W/m² heat density, was that the temperature signal of row #4 had increased. Figure 4 shows the Fourier transform for amplitude and phase of the heating wave between two simulations SL12 and SL16. Using these additional data processing methods more defects can be revealed in the equivalent images.

Table 3: Settings for optical lockin thermography simulation used on the sandwich CF-PET-CF sample and results

Simulation #	Heating density (W/m ²)	Total Heating time (s)	Time step (s)	No. defects detected	Detection depth limit
SL1 ⁶	3000	30	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL2	6000	20	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL3	6000	30	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL4	6000	30	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL5	6000	60	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL6	6000	90	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL7	6000	120	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL8	11111	30	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL9	11111	60	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL10	11111	60	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL11	11111	90	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL12	11111	120	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL13	22222	30	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL14	22222	60	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL15	22222	90	0.5	12/15	5mm
SL16	22222	120	0.5	12/15	5mm

Figure 3. Thermal image taken at 120s and spatial profiles of simulation SL12.

6 SL= Sandwich lockin

Figure 4. FT from simulation SL16 and SL12. Left 22222 W/m² and right 11111 W/m² at 120sec total heating

3.2 Pulsed thermography simulations for sandwich CFRP-PET component

The next IRT technique that was used was pulsed thermography. Table 4 presents the settings and the results of the different simulations that were carried out. Compared to optical lockin technique, pulsed thermography simulations seemed to give worse results from a quantitative perspective. In the first simulations (SP1-3) that were carried out at 11,111,111 W/m² heat density, realistic times of 3-6 ms were used, which are typical heating times for pulsed thermography. SP 1-3 provided defect detection only up to 3.75mm. Under these test conditions, row #4 only gave very faint Delta T signals, thus leading to increase heating time in simulations that were followed. Consequently, heating density was lowered and heating time increased to still follow realistic settings. Detection of row #4 was important in order to be able to detect disbonds between front skin and the PET foam core. Time steps under pulsed thermography simulations were very important in order to provide accuracy in the calculations. Consequently, the computation time steps were equal to the heating time. This meant that simulations took considerably longer to compute, up to 1h, even in PCs with high computing power. Time steps for example in the region of 1s did not provide any detection of defects. Experimenting with the observation time revealed that longer time was required to improve row #4 detection, hence simulations with longer total time were carried out.

Table 4. Settings for pulsed thermography simulation used on the sandwich CF-PET-CF sample and results

Simulation #	Heating density (W/m ²)	Heating time (s)	Total time (s)	Time step (s)	No. defects detected	Detection depth limit
SP1 ⁷	11,111,111	0.003	5	0.003	9/15	3.75 mm
SP2	11,111,111	0.003	10	0.003	9/15	3.75 mm
SP3	11,111,111	0.006	10	0.006	9/15	3.75 mm
SP4	1,000,000	0.05	10	0.05	9/15	3.75 mm
SP5	1,000,000	0.05	20	0.05	12/15	5 mm
SP6	1,000,000	0.05	40	0.1	12/15	5 mm
SP7	1,000,000	0.05	60	0.1	12/15	5 mm
SP8	333,000	0.1	20	0.2	12/15	5 mm
SP9	333,000	0.1	40	0.2	12/15	5 mm

⁷ Sandwich Pulsed

SP10	333,000	0.1	60	0.2	12/15	5 mm
SP11	666,000	0.1	20	0.2	12/15	5 mm
SP12	666,000	0.1	40	0.2	12/15	5 mm

Figure 5. Thermal image taken at 20s and spatial profiles of simulation SP11

Results from simulation SP11 are presented in Figure 5 which provide a good balance between heating density and observation time. Longer observation time of 40s was also used at SP12, purely for the reason of improving the detection of row #4. However, raising the inspection time for the small benefits that it might offer is not in line with the fast inspection times related with pulsed thermography. Any increase beyond the heating time of 0.1sec would also be unrealistic for this type of thermography which is also known for its limitations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The current paper presented thermography modelling on a thick CFRP-PET sandwich component, that can potentially find usage in new composite rail carbody shells, with the aim of proving that specific IRT techniques such as optical lockin and pulsed thermography can detect defects in such components. The defect/damage detection especially during maintenance is of great importance for rail systems manufacturers of new composite carbodies, in case they are to introduce such new vehicles into the market. The results from the IRT simulation showed that optical lockin offers better detection of defects on the sample compared to the optical pulsed thermography technique. The 5mm thickness of the CFRP skins on the sandwich component did not prove to pose a significant problem in defect detection. Both IRT techniques were able to detect defects up to 5mm in the front CFRP skin including the disbonds between front CF skin and PET foam core. However, detecting disbonds at the back CF skin of the sandwich component, only through one sided inspection, has proven to be challenging thus leading to no detection of this particular defects. This was caused by the PET foam core and its thermal properties thus making this material a major obstacle in heat propagation. Longer times could have been used in the simulations in order to see at what point in time, or if any detection is possible at all for those deeper defects at 35mm. Instead, it was decided to keep the heating time at realistic levels in order to align with how long inspection times of a carbody in real life would take. From a quantitative perspective, optical lockin gave better results compared to pulsed thermography, based on the Delta T values that were obtained during the simulations. Although, the results tables that were presented showed that most heating settings showed defect detection, this was based on whether there was enough temperature difference (at least above 0.01°C) to cause a spike in the temperature rise graphs. Under real life conditions this detection would be more difficult and would depend on the abilities of the IR camera that is being used. Very low temperature signals of 0.03 °C or even less would probably be undetected unless the IR camera had a very low Noise Equivalent Temperature Difference (NETD) of less than 30mk. Even with a low NETD IR camera, noise of \pm NETD/2 would make many of these defects undetectable. IRT simulations are typically without noise thus an addition of 20 percent noise in the data could be part of further research work.

The current work remains a proof of concept of how optical lockin and pulsed thermography can be applied to detect defects in thick composite sandwich components of the aforementioned material nature. Further work is to be carried out in lab environment as part of the GEARBODIES EU funded project to prove the ability of those IRT techniques.

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